

2,4,6-Trimethylpyridine Complexes of Copper(II)carboxylates

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Manuscript received 5 December 1983, revised 28 May 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

A series of adducts of copper(II)carboxylates of general formula, $[\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2(2,4,6\text{-Me}_3\text{Py})_n]$ (where $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, ClC_6H_4 , ClCH_2 , Cl_2CH ; and $n=1$ or 2) have been synthesised. Magnetic and spectral studies reveal that 1:1 adducts are binuclear carboxylate bridged species whereas 1:2 adducts have a mononuclear square planar configuration involving unidentate carboxylate groups except the copper(II) monochloroacetate complex which has a six-coordinate distorted octahedral structure in which the carboxylate group behaves as a bidentate chelating ligand.

2,4,6-TRIMETHYLPYRIDINE like so many other mono- and di-substituted pyridines has been largely employed as a ligand for the preparation of transition metal complexes¹⁻³. But not much work has appeared in literature on its complexes with copper(II)carboxylates except one or two isolated reports⁴. Consequently, a number of such adducts with copper(II)arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates have been prepared and characterised.

Experimental

Copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H., AnalaR) was used as such. Basic copper(II) carbonate, $\text{CuCO}_3 \cdot \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.) was purified by repeated washings with hot water. Carboxylic acids (B.D.H.) were used as such. 2,4,6-Me₃Py was fractionally distilled after keeping it over potassium hydroxide pellets overnight. Solvents were purified by conventional methods. Copper(II)arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates were prepared by the standard methods^{5,6}.

Bis(benzoato)2,4,6-trimethylpyridine copper(II) : A solution of copper(II)benzoate (3.05 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (150 ml) was shaken vigorously with 2,4,6-Me₃Py (1.21 g, 0.01 mol). The filtrate on concentration and cooling deposited green crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot \text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$ separated, was washed with acetone and dried over calcium chloride at room temperature.

Bis(o-methylbenzoato)bis(2,4,6-trimethylpyridine) copper(II) : To a solution of copper(II) o-methylbenzoate (3.33 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (150 ml) 2,4,6-Me₃Py (3.02 g, 0.025 mol) was added and the content was refluxed for 15 min over a water-bath and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to one-tenth of its volume and allowed to cool to deposit violet crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3\text{-o})_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{N})_2$ which were separated by filtration and dried over calcium chloride.

The remaining complexes were prepared by the similar procedure.

Analysis : Copper was estimated gravimetrically as cuprous thiocyanate. Carbon and hydrogen were determined in the micro-analytical laboratory of the department.

Physical measurements : Molar conductance of the complexes was determined on millimolar solutions in 1,4-dioxane and methanol using Elico CM82T conductivity bridge. Magnetic moments were determined by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra were scanned on a Beckman D.B. spectrophotometer in chloroform. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 ultraviolet, visible and near-infrared spectrophotometer. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP2000 spectrophotometer.

The analytical data, magnetic and electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 1. Important infrared bands of the ligand and its adducts with their tentative assignments are quoted in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results (Table 1) show that 2,4,6-trimethylpyridine (2,4,6-Me₃Py) with copper(II)-arylcarboxylates and chloroacetates gives rise to two types of complexes, 1:1 mono-amine complexes of formula $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2 \cdot 2,4,6\text{-Me}_3\text{Py}$, and 1:2 bis-amine complexes of composition $\text{Cu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})_2 \cdot (2,4,6\text{-Me}_3\text{Py})_2$. Mono-amine complexes are green in colour whereas bis-amine complexes are violet crystalline compounds except the adduct of copper(II)monochloroacetate which is blue. The complexes are fairly stable in air and soluble in polar organic solvents. However, the complexes are less soluble in benzene and nitro-benzene and due to their insufficient solubility in these solvents their molecular weight measurements could not

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2,4,6-Me₃Py COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES

Complex	M _p °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ _{max} nm	μ _{eff} at 298K B.M.
		Cu	O	H		
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·C ₆ H ₁₁ N	193	14.59 (14.89)	61.68 (61.89)	4.73 (4.92)	710 ^a (375 sh)	1.48
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (OH ₂ -o)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	131	11.39 (11.04)	66.49 (66.72)	5.99 (6.25)	680 ^b 535 ^a (610 sh)	1.91
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃ -m)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	178	10.94 (11.04)	66.53 (66.72)	6.13 (6.25)	680 ^b	1.88
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (OH ₂ -p)) ₂ ·C ₆ H ₁₁ N	—	13.90 (13.97)	63.24 (63.37)	5.29 (5.50)	692 ^b	1.48
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (Cl-o)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	174	10.02 (10.30)	58.12 (58.39)	4.67 (4.86)	686 ^b	2.06
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (Cl-m)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	175	10.09 (10.30)	58.21 (58.39)	4.78 (4.86)	525 ^a (615 sh)	1.88
Cu(O ₂ CCH ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	185	12.59 (12.90)	48.51 (48.73)	5.03 (5.27)	704 ^b	1.98
Cu(O ₂ COHCl ₂) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	170	11.10 (11.31)	42.56 (42.74)	3.98 (4.27)	692 ^b	1.99

^aDiffuse reflectance spectra. ^bIn CHCl₃, sh=shoulder.

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF 2,4,6-Me₃Py AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES

Compd.	C-H def	Ring def	Ring breathing	C-H def	Ring def	ν _{asym} (COO)	ν _{sym} (COO)	Δν(COO)
2,4,6-Me ₃ Py	724	842	998	1157	1443	—	—	—
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₅) ₂ ·C ₆ H ₁₁ N	682	842	1028	1230	1470	1630	1400	230
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃ -o)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	688	850	1030	1235	1458	1615	1380	235
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃ -m)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	680	860	1040	1220	1470	1615	1382	233
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (OH ₂ -p)) ₂ ·C ₆ H ₁₁ N	695	848	1030	1248	1450	1610	1390	220
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (Cl-o)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	685	855	1035	1245	1468	1615	1382	233
Cu(O ₂ CC ₆ H ₄ (Cl-m)) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	700	850	1035	1250	1470	1620	1380	240
Cu(O ₂ CCH ₂ Cl) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	700	850	1035	1250	1468	1590	1410	180
Cu(O ₂ COHCl ₂) ₂ ·2C ₆ H ₁₁ N	700	852	1032	1222	1465	1645	1378	267

*Out-of-plane. **In-plane.

be done cryoscopically. Their molar conductance values lie in the range 0.032-0.096 and 26.51-71.86 Ω⁻¹cm² mol⁻¹ in 1,4-dioxane and methanol, respectively suggesting that the complexes are non-ionic in nature^{7,8}.

Magnetic moments: The 1:1 adducts of copper(II)benzoate and *p*-methylbenzoate exhibit sub-normal magnetic moments of 1.48 and 1.49 B.M., respectively. These values suggest that the complexes are dimeric and have a structure in which two copper(II) ions are bridged by four syn-syn carboxylate groups similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate⁹ having sizeable spin-exchange between the two adjacent copper(II) ions of the dimeric molecule.

The magnetic moments of 1:2 adducts fall in the range 1.88-2.66 B.M. (Table 1). These values are similar to those observed for magnetically dilute mononuclear copper(II)carboxylate complexes and suggest that these complexes are either four-coordinate square planar or six-coordinate distorted octahedral in stereochemistry¹⁰.

Electronic spectra: 1:1 Complexes exhibit a broad absorption band around 700 nm characteristic of distorted octahedral stereochemistry which is

assigned to dxz, dyz→d_{x²-y²} transition. Copper(II)-benzoate complex exhibits an additional band at 375 nm. This band appears as a shoulder on the stronger charge transfer band and is assigned to a charge transfer transition¹¹.

The visible absorption spectra of 1:2 adducts (Table 1) show significant differences in solid state and in solution implying that the structure of these complexes in the two phases may not be identical¹². The violet complexes in their diffuse reflectance spectra exhibit a band around 530 nm with a shoulder towards lower energy side. Since violet colour and absorption in the vicinity of 550 nm are characteristic of four-coordinate square-planar copper(II) complexes^{13,14}, the present complexes may be regarded to have a square-planar structure in solid state. Whether these square-planar complexes are of *cis*- or *trans*-configuration is difficult to decide unless their structures are determined by X-ray diffraction studies. In their solution spectra these complexes show a broad band around 690 nm which being a characteristic of distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹⁵ indicates that square-planar complexes in solution acquire a tetragonally distorted octahedral configuration on account of solvent coordination.

Infrared spectra: Most of the infrared bands due to free 2,4,6-Me₃Py appear in the complexes at considerably altered frequencies (Table 2) suggest that the ligand coordinates to the metal ion through its nitrogen atom in these systems. The frequency difference, Δ between the symmetric and asymmetric COO stretching frequencies is 220-230 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). These values are quite similar to those observed for other binuclear carboxylate bridged copper(II)arylcarboxylate complexes containing terminal ligands¹⁰⁻¹⁸ and points towards their dimeric syn-syn carboxylate bridged configuration. In 1 : 2 violet complexes the frequency difference, Δ is of the order of 233-267 cm⁻¹ which is higher than that found for above mentioned carboxylate bridged complexes. Since a large splitting of the carboxyl stretching frequency is often taken as an indication of monodentate coordination of the carboxylate group¹⁹, it is concluded that the present violet complexes may also be square-planar in which the carboxylate group is monodentate. In contrast, the Δ value for the blue 1 : 2 monochloroacetate complex is lower than the values observed in carboxylate complexes containing monodentate or bidentate bridging carboxylate groups. This indicates that in the 1 : 2 adduct carboxylate groups have a bidentate chelating configuration, thereby conferring a six-coordinate distorted octahedral environment on copper(II).

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